

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D3.1: Comprehensive plan for capacity building activities and training pills delivery (I)

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

4H	Quadruple helix
CfP	Call for Proposal
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EIC	European Innovation Council
EnOLL	European Network of Living Labs
ESCO	European Standard Classification of Occupations
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

SUMMARY

This Deliverable is the first step towards the development of capacity building for col-labers – socio-digital entrepreneurs who will be trained to boost local ecosystems and social-business bi-directional innovation dynamics. A comprehensive plan will be elaborated on and submitted in August 2023. These deliverables aim to enable the delivery of a curriculum and training pills in January 2024 ultimately.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation ecosystems in European regions

There are approximately two million social economy enterprises in Europe, representing 10% of all businesses in the EU. Achieving the triple transition “green, digital and social” demands a paramount effort for including, in a more decisive manner, social economy enterprises, social innovators and entrepreneurs in our EU innovation ecosystems.

INTEGER, a Horizon Europe project that kicked-off on 14th-15th of February in Barcelona (Spain), addresses following questions:

- How can we actively integrate social innovation actors in European innovation ecosystems? Or better, how can we get social and business-driven innovators to work together?

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of **healthy living and wellbeing**, INTEGER will bring forward three innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive and integrative EU innovation ecosystems:

- The INTEGER 4 Helix Collaboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the ‘**Col-laboratories**’ (common open house of all kinds of innovators and entrepreneurs interested in producing new products and services that come from business or social oriented innovation).
- An EU Healthy Living Collaboratory, a true **network of networks’ community** with the capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects.
- A new professional profile, the ‘**Col-laber**’ or ‘**Col-laboratory manager**’ as a multiplying agent of change in these integrated innovation ecosystems.

Col-laborathons will be held in 3 EU Regions (Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow) to foster social innovation Minimum Viable Products and Services to upscale it throughout Europe by applying and testing the INTEGER 4H comprehensive model.

By facilitating **business-driven** and **social-driven innovations**, INTEGER seeks to accelerate new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, groundbreaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptaking and exploitation dynamics.

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INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This document describes the background and planning for the upcoming capacity building activities and the cooperative development of training-pills. Task 3.1 focuses on the co-creation of digital arenas for capacity building among innovator actors in the three regions with a twofold axis: a) Bringing attention to the benefits of social innovation projects to the society through capacity building, and b) Developing business support services for social entrepreneurs (templates, manuals and other support material).

This deliverable starts in section 1 with a plan for building digital arenas among innovator actors in the three regions. Then section 2 focuses on developing the profile of the col-labber (the social-digital entrepreneur who works on social innovation projects and enables the building of ecosystems) and its approach for capacity building including skills, qualifications, learning outcomes and curriculum. Section 3 focuses on the delivery of the training pills which are intended to provide valuable information in a short and easy-to-understand way. This deliverable (D3.1) aims to provide an overall plan of the capacity building activities and training pills delivery. D3.1 will be followed by D3.2: A more comprehensive plan for capacity building activities and training pills delivery (II) in Month 7. The business support services for social entrepreneurs will be made available after the comprehensive planning for the period between Months 12-24 by Work Package Leader URV.

Together with the support of the partners, the aim is to specifically address the different areas of the quadruple helix model (social innovation organisations; government; industry; academia) and bring them towards the benefits of social innovation. The knowledge gained from the European collaborathons, where knowledge transfer between the four helices will take place, will be used to process generally valid and effective information in the training pills as well as in the capacity building activities.

The purpose of the training pills and the capacity building activities is to implement a bi-directional user-centric approach to offer the communities of social innovation actors the suitable business and professional skills to market themselves and enhance the collaboration between social innovators and actors of the innovation ecosystem. Besides, they will also focus on training the business-driven innovation actors to broaden their scope and understand better the needs of social innovators and entrepreneurs to access other sources of funding.

The following chapters successively describe the planning for digital arenas, the col-labber professional profile and the training pills.

1.3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

The task is embedded in WP3, the building of the col-laborathons and is strongly related to the activities of WP5, WP2 and the actions, such as the study visits under WP3.

The communication channels developed in WP5 will be used for the dissemination of the training pills as well as for the approach of cooperating partners in capacity building. The website is also needed to make the training pills available on a permanent basis, fostering longer-term impact and sustainability.

In addition, the information from both WP2 and WP3 will be of significant use to incorporate the developed information of the project into the training pills and capacity building.

2 Building digital arenas

During the study visits and meetings in Catalunya, Krakow and Hamburg in February and March 2023, the first steps were already made towards a peer-to-peer collaboration model between business and social innovation actors and organisations at local/regional level and inter-regions. During the meetings, representatives of citizens, businesses (social, technological and financial), authorities and science presented their businesses and activities. For more details of the meetings see the Study Visits Reports at the project website: <https://integercollab.eu>.

With the study visit meetings as a starting point, WP 3 will further build on the realisation of the INTEGER 4H Healthy Living Collaboratory. To achieve this, the following activities are foreseen:

- a) Creating local/regional spaces on the [thelocal.network](#) platform, specifically designed for building up the INTEGER community and quadruple helix col-laboratori. This is a place where people can meet and exchange in their own languages on questions, needs, demands and provisions at local or regional level, interregional or EU levels.

Channels

Browse through the different channels that group the information published in the community in a thematic way. Subscribe to receive notifications and not miss any news.

General

Regional

Becoming a member of theglocal.network benefits to an early access to contact details of local/regional partners, local/regional funding programmes, inspirational cases, activities, innovations, developments and networking opportunities:

- a) Online international, regional or local meetings with INTEGER internal and external members through the glocal.network on (among others) the following topics:
 - a. The power of social innovation
 - b. Quality of life of citizens
 - c. Healthy living
 - d. Digitalisation
 - e. Profitable social innovation
 - f. (Social) Business development
- b) Forums in national languages on the INTEGER platform where members can meet and exchange (for mutual benefit).
- c) Templates and manuals for business development.

The Digital arenas and forums will be realised in June 2023. The webinars and other activities will take place in September and beyond.

3 Capacity building programme for quadruple helix communities

Capacity building for quadruple helix communities involves developing the necessary skills, knowledge, and resources for all stakeholders to effectively participate in the innovation process. Some key elements of capacity building for quadruple helix communities include:

Developing collaboration and communication skills: This involves promoting effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders from different sectors to facilitate knowledge sharing, problem-solving, and innovation.

1. **Enhancing innovation and entrepreneurship skills:** This involves providing training and resources to stakeholders to promote innovation and entrepreneurship, and to help them identify and develop new opportunities.
2. **Building relationships, networks and partnerships:** This involves developing and strengthening networks and partnerships among stakeholders to enhance knowledge exchange and collaboration.
3. **Fostering a culture of openness and trust:** This involves creating a culture of openness and trust among stakeholders to promote knowledge sharing, collaboration, and innovation.
4. **Developing policies and frameworks that support quadruple helix collaboration:** This involves developing policies and frameworks that support and promote quadruple helix collaboration and innovation, and that provide incentives for stakeholders to participate in the process.

By building capacity in these areas, quadruple helix communities can effectively harness the collective knowledge, skills, and resources of all stakeholders to drive innovation and positive change.

INTEGER will design targeted capacity building and learning pills for the Col·labor profile so that we train the new generation of facilitators knows how to facilitate the process of 4H collaboration.

4 Col·laber – the new professional profile

4.1 Introduction

INTEGER aims to develop capacity building for a new profile of professionals: the col·laber: the new generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and ecosystems' enablers. In this chapter we focus on the plan to define the col·laber profile, the expected learning outcomes of the capacity building activities and the approach to offer the learning facilities.

4.2 Professional profile of the col·laber

Col·labers in the INTEGER project are social innovators with digital skills who are able to network and realise ecosystems, perform matchmaking activities and bring together business and technological innovators and are able to set up sustainable innovation quadruple helix co-creation arenas where socio-digital and business-driven innovations could thrive. This is in a nutshell how the col·laber profile will look like.

During the INTEGER project, this profile will be further elaborated. This will be executed by consulting the European Standard Classification of Occupations (ESCO), in the pillar of occupations. The ESCO classification identifies and categorises skills, competences, and occupations relevant for the EU labour market and education and training. The occupation pillar organises the occupation concepts in ESCO. It uses hierarchical relationships between them, metadata as well as mappings to the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO) to structure the employment [1]. The second approach to define the profile of the col·laber will be performed by involving the partners of the three ecosystems of the INTEGER project: Barcelona, Hamburg and Krakow. Members of the ecosystem will be interviewed or invited for a survey to co-create the col·laber profile.

The profile of the col·laber will be finalised during an online consortium meeting in June 2023.

4.3 Col·laber skills and competences

After the joint definition of the col·laber's profile, the appropriate skills and competences of the col·laber will be elaborated by the task leader. The ESCO Classification database [2] will be used to appropriately define the skills and competences.

The ESCO skills and competences pillar distinguishes between i) skill/competence concepts and ii) knowledge concepts by indicating the skill type. Every concept also includes an explanation in the form of a description.

The skills pillar of ESCO contains 13,485 concepts structured in a hierarchy which contains four sub-classifications. Each sub-classification targets different types of knowledge and skill/competence concepts:

- Knowledge
- Skills
- Attitudes and values
- Language skills and knowledge

In addition to the hierarchy, subsets of skills can be accessed through:

- A transversal skill hierarchy
- A collection of languages
- A collection of digital skills

The task leader will propose the appropriate set of skills to the consortium. The set of skills will be jointly assessed and approved in an online consortium meeting in **September 2023**.

4.3 Col-laber learning outcomes and goals

After the definition of the col.laber occupation and col-laber skills, the task leader will focus on the qualifications. Qualifications are the formal outcome of an assessment and validation process which is obtained when a competent body determines that an individual has achieved learning outcomes to given standards.[3]

Information on qualifications at European level is now displayed in Europass [4] and comes from databases of national qualifications reflecting the National Qualifications Frameworks that are owned and managed by the European Member States. Europass offers the most up to date and rich repository of high-quality data on qualifications, national qualification frameworks and learning opportunities in Europe, helping learners to find a course in another country and employers to grasp the value of a qualification from a different EU Member State.

Using the skills and qualifications, the task leader will define the learning outcomes and goals for the capacity building activities for the INTEGER col-laber profile. To define the expected learning outcomes, we will use Bloom's Taxonomy.[5] Bloom's Taxonomy is a classification of the different outcomes and skills that educators set for their students (learning outcomes). The taxonomy was proposed in 1956 by Benjamin Bloom, an educational psychologist at the University of Chicago. The terminology has been recently updated to include the following six levels of learning. These 6 levels can be used to structure the learning outcomes, lessons and assessments of capacity building activities.

Bloom's Taxonomy:

Remembering: Retrieving, recognizing, and recalling relevant knowledge from long-term memory.

Understanding: Constructing meaning from oral, written, and graphic messages through interpreting, exemplifying, classifying, summarising, inferring, comparing, and explaining.

Applying: Carrying out or using a procedure for executing or implementing.

Analysing: Breaking material into constituent parts, determining how the parts relate to one another and to an overall structure or purpose through differentiating, organising, and attributing.

Evaluating: Making judgments based on criteria and standards through checking and critiquing.

Creating: Putting elements together to form a coherent or functional whole; reorganising elements into a new pattern or structure through generating, planning, or producing.

Like other taxonomies, Bloom's is hierarchical, meaning that learning at the higher levels is dependent on having attained prerequisite knowledge and skills at lower levels. Bloom's Taxonomy is often displayed as a pyramid graphic to help demonstrate this hierarchy.

Figure 1: Bloom's Taxonomy hierarchy

The definition of the qualifications and expected learning outcomes will be jointly approved by the consortium in **October 2023**.

4.4 Col·labor curriculum

The final step in the INTEGER Capacity building approach is the search for appropriate training and learning opportunities to become a col·laborer: the social innovator with digital skills who is able to realise ecosystems.

To define the col·laborer curriculum, the task leader will perform an extensive search on the following websites:

- Erasmus+, EU programme for education, training, youth and sport, Project Results website. This website provides every single training and learning result that has been developed in the EU Erasmus+ programme.[6]
- Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe, EPALE [7]. EPALE is a European, multilingual, open membership community of adult learning professionals, including adult educators and trainers, guidance and support staff, researchers and academics, and policymakers.
- The European Network of Living Labs (EnOLL) Learning Lab [8].
- European Education Area [9], Vocational education and training initiatives and Adult Learning.

Keywords are the skills, learning outcomes and qualifications defined in earlier stages. The found results will be thoroughly tested by the task leader. Consortium partners may be consulted about the appropriateness of found results.

The result of the searches and tests will be a set of open access training and learning opportunities that further support the capacity building of collaborators. The links to these training and learning opportunities will be published on the INTEGER platform (theglobal.network) and the website (see next chapter).

The final result is due in **December 2023**.

5 Training pills

5.1 Training pills in INTEGER

Training Pills are one of the most attractive formats in micro-learning. They are small content units linked to a question. Their aim is to impart knowledge in a quick, effective and attractive way for the user. Short videos are usually used as the medium.

In the INTEGER project, the training pills are to be created as short learning videos (maximum 2 minutes) that address specific target groups of the quadruple Helix. They are also meant to further support the capacity building activities, by giving knowledge incentives to possible collaborators. The videos will always deal with a question followed by a brief explanation of the problem and an explanation of a possible solution. The training pill concludes with a call-to-action that draws the viewers' attention to the INTEGER project.

Specific training pills will be developed by bringing attention to the benefits of social innovation to the society. These will include questions that actors coming from each of the quadruple helices have towards social innovation projects. A total of 13 training pills was promised in the proposal, of which 8 videos must include INTEGER partners and at least 5 videos must include experts. We foresee 14 training pills at this moment.

Proposed topics for training pills. The topics are collected from the study visits to Barcelona, Krakow and Hamburg. When the training pills are finalised, they will be published in groups on the INTEGER website:

1. What is social innovation and why is it important?
2. How to become a social innovator, a facilitator of quadruple helix communities in the field of health and wellbeing?
3. How to make social innovation in the field of healthy living and wellbeing sustainable?
4. How to find investors for social innovation?
5. How to apply for public funding for social innovation?
6. How to generate impact with social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing?
7. How to make successes of social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing visible?
8. How can a public authority benefit from social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing?
9. How can academia benefit from social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing?
10. How can technological businesses benefit from social innovation?
11. How can financial businesses benefit from social innovation?
12. How to involve stakeholders from the quadruple helix in co-creating social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing and keep them interested over time?

13. How to identify similar initiatives in other regions and exchange knowledge, network and matchmaking?
14. How a col·laborer could make the facilitation in the glocal.network?

5.2 Content development and timeplan

The content of each training pill will be prepared by the task leader. Scripts of each topic will be written out. Each training pill will have approximately:

Problem, Question and Answer. In learning videos, a *problem* is first described, leading to a *question* and an *answer* is given. Example:

- 6 PROBLEM - *"It seems so difficult to apply for public funding."*
- 7 QUESTION - *"How to apply for public funding?"*
- 8 ANSWER – *"It is easier than expected, you just have to..."*

Regarding a time plan for the training pill delivery, the training pill scripts should be completely ready by **September 2023**. As soon as a script for a pill is finished, it will also be sent to the respective partner to have it checked before creating the necessary video.

Example Training pill 1

Question: What is social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing and why is it important?

Answer: Provided by an expert, for example of the Nudge Institute/ Centre for Social Innovation [10]. For example: *Social innovation refers to the process of developing and implementing new, effective solutions to solve social and environmental issues. Social needs should be better met than it has been done before. You could also say that social innovation is nothing more than using the tools you have for the good of your society. The concept has existed since ancient times, but has acquired new meaning in today's world. Social innovators use every resource at their disposal to help their fellow man.*

Social innovation is important because it is trying to solve neglected problems. Truth be told, social innovations are all around us. Organisations like Wikipedia or microcredit banks work to meet needs and improve people's lives. Phone helplines save lives when needed, and online forums offer specialised help. Across the world, thousands of small bits of social innovation work to make life easier.

So far, social innovation has been relatively small-scale. But now, with problems growing in scale, developing social innovation has become an urgent task. Currently, the problems we face are far larger in scale than the solutions we have. To that end, social innovators must start figuring out how to help for example for healthy living and wellbeing. To learn more about social innovation, go to

This training pill will be accompanied by pictures and vectors of social innovation as mentioned above, plus voluntary people who clean the streets from trash, take care of children or older people.

Such scripts will be developed for each training pill.

Experts and partners will be invited to contribute with sentences that will be recorded. If technically feasible, the records will be accompanied by written texts of the spoken words.

Other aspects of the training pill delivery

All training pills will be made as short videos. They will become available in the English language (in some cases this can be recorded or subtitled in some languages of the participating regions).

By filming against a green or white background, an integer background can be inserted when editing the videos. In addition to a short introductory image, an end screen should also be inserted that refers the viewer to the INTEGER website.

Additional Content. To make the Training pill videos even more attractive, a small text, a tutorial or a picture could be developed for each video if feasible. Formats such as STEP by STEP instructions or infographics increase the learning effect of the training pills and are made available or displayed with the videos.

6 Conclusions and Timeplan

This Deliverable is the first step towards the development of capacity building for col-labers – socio-digital entrepreneurs who will be trained to boost local ecosystems and social-business bi-directional innovation dynamics. A comprehensive plan will be elaborated on and submitted in August 2023. These deliverables aim to enable the delivery of a curriculum and training pills in January 2024 ultimately.

The timeline of the work plan is described:

June 2023	Set-up of the digital arenas Capacity building: Create a professional profile for the col-laber.
September 2023	Digital arena activities Define skills and competences for the col-laber. Training pills: Finalise all scripts for the planned training pills.
October 2023	Define learning outcomes and goals for the col-laber.
November 2023	Digital arena activities
December 2023	Finalise the col-laber curriculum.
February 2024	Digital arena activities Training pills: Upload all Training pills to the INTEGER website.

After the first year of the project, we will further build on providing the templates (Task 3.1, part b), the organisation of digital arena activities and the motivation of the network.

7 REFERENCES

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